

Balancing urban growth and environmental change: Land use patterns in Tehran and Sydney

Alireza Dehghani^{a,*}, Ali Soltani^{b,c,d}, Kobra Nateghi^e

^a University of Guilan, Rasht, Iran

^b College of Science and Engineering, Flinders University, Adelaide, 5042, Australia

^c Le Studium Loire Valley Institute for Advanced Studies, Orléans, France

^d CEDETE Research Center, University of Orléans, Orléans, France

^e University of Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran

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ABSTRACT

The large-scale conversion of agricultural, forest, and bare lands into urban areas is a defining feature of contemporary metropolitan expansion, reshaping natural landscapes and altering land cover patterns. This study examines the spatial and temporal dynamics of Land Use and Land Cover Change (LULCC) in Tehran, Iran, and Sydney, Australia, over a 30-year period (1993-2023), emphasizing shifts from natural land cover to the built environment. By employing multi-source spatial data and comparative analysis, we identify distinct urbanization trends and transformation pathways in both cities. Tehran has undergone more extensive and accelerated land conversion, with a pronounced shift from agricultural land and bare soil to built-up areas, reflecting rapid and intensive urban growth. In contrast, Sydney's land development strategies have been more structured, prioritizing the retention of agricultural land while directing urban expansion toward previously bare or disturbed areas. Intensity analysis reveals that Tehran's LULCC is not only faster but also more extensive, leading to a more fragmented landscape with a higher proportion of built-up land. Logistic regression analysis indicates that access to road networks is a major driver of land conversion in both cities, shaping the spatial distribution of urban growth. FLUS model projections for 2035 suggest that, without regulatory interventions, Tehran will continue to experience high rates of agricultural and bare land loss, reinforcing urban expansion trends. These findings highlight the need for strategic land-use planning to manage urbanization sustainably, drawing insights from Sydney's more regulated approach. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of LULCC patterns in rapidly developing metropolitan regions, offering valuable perspectives for urban and regional planning efforts.

1. Introduction

Land Use and Land Cover Change (LULCC) has emerged as a critical concern for metropolitan areas worldwide, driven by rapid urbanization that has significantly increased the demand for urban land, especially in developing countries (Lamchin et al., 2022b). Urbanization-driven LULCC leads to habitat destruction, biodiversity loss, ecosystem fragmentation, and resource depletion (Antonio Chaparro Torres et al., 2024). It exacerbates flooding, pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, and the urban heat island effect (Gupta et al., 2022; Omar & Kumar, 2021; Azhdari et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2022), altering microclimates and stressing ecosystems (Liu et al., 2024). These impacts extend beyond urban areas, affecting hydrological cycles, carbon storage, and overall

ecosystem resilience (Das et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2023).

Quantifying LULCC is essential for analyzing land transformation trends and understanding the underlying factors driving these changes (Soltani et al., 2025b). This process plays a crucial role in evaluating the effects of LULCC on ecosystem services and forecasting future land use shifts. A precise measurement of land change is vital not only for detecting patterns but also for comprehensively understanding the broader implications across various spatial and temporal scales (Deng and Quan, 2023). A critical aspect of LULCC analysis is identifying whether the detected changes exhibit systematic transitions. In cases where transitions within a category are not random but occur in a predictable, structured manner, it becomes crucial to understand the factors driving such systematic changes (Alo and Pontius, 2008). For example,

* Corresponding author. Department of Urban Planning, Faculty of Art and Architecture, University of Guilan, Rasht, Iran.

¹ a.dehghani@webmail.guilan.ac.ir

land use in certain areas may consistently transition from natural to urban due to growing population pressures, or from agricultural to industrial due to economic shifts (Teixeira et al., 2014). By identifying these systematic patterns, researchers can better understand how the area covered by specific land categories evolves over time and predict future changes. This understanding is pivotal for planning and implementing targeted strategies to manage land-use change and mitigate its potential impacts on ecosystems and urban development.

While LULCC concerns have attracted significant global attention and research efforts, the patterns, processes, and driving forces of LULCC vary depending on the region's development stage (Chen et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2022). Developed countries have witnessed a trend of stabilization or even a slight reversal in LULCC rates in recent decades (Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011; Radwan et al., 2021). In contrast, developing countries face a particularly pressing challenge due to the unprecedented pace of LULCC in their rapidly growing metropolitan areas. This phenomenon, exceeding historical trends, is driven by societal development and population growth (Kamran et al., 2023), increasing the demand for amenities, facilities, and housing. Such demand fuels urban sprawl, often encroaching on natural landscapes (Yue et al., 2019). Economic development further intensifies LULCC as cities expand to accommodate industries and businesses, usually converting agricultural land and natural habitats (Lambin and Geist, 2008). Additionally, rural-to-urban migration intensifies pressure on land resources as people seek employment opportunities in urban centers, accelerating urbanization (Mahtta et al., 2022; Seto et al., 2011). These rapid transformations are often exacerbated by weak policy and management structures, including inadequate land-use planning, ineffective zoning regulations, and insufficient enforcement of environmental regulations (Farrell, 2017; Sheppard, 2010).

In this paper, Sydney has been selected as the context representing a developed nation alongside Tehran, allowing for narrative analysis exploration of urbanization and LULCC. Despite differences in geography, history, and land use, comparing Tehran (developing) and Sydney (developed) helps isolate universal vs. context-specific urbanization drivers. Tehran's expansion is driven by informal settlements and high population density (Dadashpoor et al., 2019, while Sydney's follows a regulated growth model with green infrastructure policies (García-Álvarez et al., 2022). This contrast clarifies the global pressures of urbanization, such as population growth, versus localized policy impacts that shape land-use transformations. Governance and economic status also play a critical role, as seen in Sydney's structured planning (The 2017 Metropolitan Water Plan, 2017) compared to Tehran's fragmented urban policies, highlighting how institutional frameworks mediate housing and land-use demands. This study aims to identify transferable lessons for sustainable development and advance cross-context methodological analysis. Sydney's success in green space preservation (Green Grid) offers insights for Tehran's ecological balance, while Tehran's challenges with informal settlements provide warnings for rapidly growing cities in the Global South. Additionally, by applying intensity analysis and FLUS modeling across two distinct urban environments, the study tests the robustness of these tools beyond homogeneous regions (Seto et al., 2011). While geographic and historical differences exist, this study leverages them to examine scaling effects in urban expansion. Tehran's high-intensity, low-regulation growth contrasts with Sydney's low-intensity, high-regulation model, demonstrating how economic stages shape land-use outcomes. Furthermore, both cities face the global challenge of achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, yet their differing approaches underscore the need for regionalized SDG strategies that account for local governance, economic constraints, and urban dynamics. This study advances our understanding of LULCC in the context of rapidly growing metropolitan areas, specifically by comparing the dynamics between a developing city (Tehran) and a developed city (Sydney). The objectives of this study are to:

- Identify and quantify the intensity and magnitude of LULCC and their impact on landscape patterns and continuity
- Measure the patterns and process of urban expansion
- Distinguish between systematic and random LULCC in urban areas and determine the driving factors behind these changes
- Compare the similarities and differences in LULCC patterns and processes between Tehran and Sydney

By identifying the drivers of land-use changes and differentiating systematic from random urban expansions, the study equips policy-makers with actionable knowledge to promote sustainable urban growth in rapidly expanding cities like Tehran. The predictive modeling of future land-use changes enhances long-term urban planning strategies, enabling the mitigation of urban sprawl and the preservation of agricultural and green spaces. The comparative analysis between Tehran and Sydney also underscores shared and distinct urbanization challenges in developing and developed cities, fostering cross-context learning.

2. Literature review

LULC changes, encompassing physical cover and human land use, are driven by natural and human factors, including climate change (Seto et al., 2011). Climate change both triggers LULC shifts via extreme events and forces urban growth through environmental degradation. Urban expansion is increasingly climate-driven, requiring resilient infrastructure and adaptive planning. Drought and desertification drive rural migration to cities, while warming exacerbates urban heat islands, influencing land-use policies (Güneralp et al., 2020; Gupta et al., 2025; Tanoori et al., 2024a, 2024b). Understanding these changes is crucial for resource management, biodiversity, and climate mitigation. Integrating climate adaptation into urban planning is essential for sustainable development (Omar et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2022).

LULCC drivers vary significantly by development context. In developing regions, rapid urbanization (Naikoo et al., 2020; Hassan, 2017) and economic globalization drive agricultural/forest conversion (Athukorala and Murayama, 2020; Bren d'Amour et al., 2017), while developed regions prioritize ecological preservation through policy (García-Álvarez et al., 2022; Seto et al., 2011). Infrastructure shapes growth patterns, from sprawl-inducing road expansions in Tehran and Nairobi (Estoque and Murayama, 2015) to Europe's sprawl-limiting transit-oriented development (Güneralp et al., 2020). Informal settlements fragment landscapes in Cairo and Mumbai (Aboulnaga et al., 2021; Agarwal et al., 2023), while climate stressors intensify urban pressures in Tehran and coastal Bangladesh (Effati et al., 2021; Hassan, 2017). Governance mediates these dynamics - developing regions often see market forces override environmental concerns, while developed areas balance growth and sustainability (Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011). Tehran exemplifies governance challenges, where centralized planning (Hosseini et al., 2016) and housing subsidies (Bagheri and Soltani, 2023) unintentionally accelerated informal settlements and agricultural loss. Conversely, Sydney's neoliberal approach prioritizes transit-oriented development and green corridors through plans like the Metropolitan Strategy (2017) and Greater Sydney Region Plan (2018), though public-private partnerships sometimes favor commercial projects over ecological needs (Bunker and Troy, 2015).

The interplay between governance structures and LULCC is critical. In Tehran, top-down decision-making and weak enforcement of zoning laws have allowed industrial and residential encroachment into greenbelts, exacerbating heat island effect (Shamaee et al., 2025). Conversely, Sydney's decentralized planning system—managed by the Greater Sydney Commission—seeks to balance growth across three “cities” (eastern, central, western) but struggles with inconsistent implementation across local councils, resulting in fragmented land-use outcomes (Pinnegar et al., 2020). Economic policies further amplify disparities: Tehran's post-sanction austerity measures diverted funds from green

infrastructure to housing crises (Effati et al., 2021), while Sydney's tax incentives (e.g., negative gearing) fueled speculative sprawl in western agricultural zones (Daley et al., 2018). In Tehran, centralized governance and weak public participation have enabled elite capture of land markets, prioritizing commercial over ecological land uses (Azizi, 1995), whereas Sydney's neoliberal planning prioritizes developer interests, sidelining marginalized communities in western suburbs (Pinnegar et al., 2020).

Effective LULCC analysis requires methods that distinguish between random and systematic conversions, which conventional approaches like Markov Chain (MC) transition matrices fail to do (Asenso Barnieh et al., 2023). MC methods are further limited by their inability to assess conversion intensity and scale (Da et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2020). Intensity Analysis addresses these gaps by systematically evaluating transformation rates across scales (Aldwaik and Pontius, 2012), revealing patterns that drive changes. Unlike size-focused traditional methods, it examines category gains/losses and enables cross-regional comparison of systematic transitions despite differing land proportions (Pontius et al., 2013; Xie et al., 2020). While random conversions occur abruptly, systematic ones reflect sustained pressures like market/demographic forces (Tong et al., 2020). Although well-theorized and widely applied in LULCC (Lamchin et al., 2022a; Teixeira et al., 2014) and urban expansion studies (Chen and Ma, 2023), its urban planning applications remain limited.

LULCC analysis combines statistical and spatial methods to examine socio-environmental drivers, including natural factors (soil, topography) and anthropogenic pressures like population growth, economic development, and urban transport (Li et al., 2020; Soltani, 2017; Omar et al., 2022). While common drivers exist globally (Allan et al., 2022; Nuissl and Siedentop, 2021), their dominance varies by context - Delhi's suburban expansion reflects migration pressures (Naikoo et al., 2020), whereas governance shapes outcomes differently in Tehran (elite-dominated land markets; Azizi, 1995) versus Sydney (developer-led neoliberal planning; Pinnegar et al., 2020).

Methodologically, studies employ LR, GWR, FA, and SEM to quantify driver impacts, yet Iranian research lags globally. Despite early Markov applications in Tehran (Arsanjani et al., 2011), advanced methods remain rare, with exceptions like CA-Markov in Mashhad (Rahnama, 2021) and InVEST-CA models in Karaj (Zarandian et al., 2023). Critical gaps persist in intensity analysis and cross-contextual comparisons (e.g., Tehran-Sydney), particularly for distinguishing systematic versus random transitions - a key contribution of this study.

3. Case studies

3.1. Tehran (Iran)

Tehran, Iran's capital, spans 1500 square kilometers and houses over 15 million people, making it one of the Middle East's most densely populated cities, after Cairo and Istanbul (Statistical Centre of Iran, 2021). Urban expansion is driven by population growth, rural-to-urban migration, and economic policies (Soltani et al., 2017). State-led industrialization in the 1980s–1990s, alongside energy and housing subsidies, fueled suburban sprawl (Ehsani, 2014; Qadikolaei et al., 2024). Economic sanctions since the 2000s have exacerbated spatial inequalities between affluent northern districts and informal southern neighborhoods. Government policies have also shaped migration and urbanization. Post-Iran-Iraq War rural development initiatives failed to curb migration due to urban-rural disparities. Shifts in fertility policies, from family planning in the 1990s to pronatalist incentives post-2010, influenced housing demand (Abbasi et al., 2002). Tehran's urban fabric blends historical architecture, modern skyscrapers, and expansive residential areas. Rapid 20th-century urbanization was spurred by rural migration for employment (Talkhabi et al., 2022). The Tehran Comprehensive Plan (1960s) aimed to manage growth but faced inefficiencies and shifting political priorities (Kazemian and Mirabedini,

2011). Privatization in the 2000s encouraged speculative real estate development at the expense of affordable housing (Hosseini et al., 2016). Land-use transformation has reshaped residential, commercial, and industrial zones, converting green spaces into urban developments, particularly in southern Tehran and Karaj, degrading ecosystems (Ghanbari et al., 2023; Dadashpoor and Panahi, 2021; Soltani et al., 2025a). Environmental policies, such as the 2017 Air Pollution Control Act, have struggled to mitigate sprawl-related pollution, reflecting the conflict between economic growth and sustainability (Shamaee et al., 2025).

3.2. Sydney (Australia)

Sydney, situated on Australia's southeastern coast and serving as the capital of New South Wales, stands as one of the country's foremost urban centers. Spanning 12,368 square kilometers with a population of 5.3 million (2022), Greater Sydney has experienced profound demographic and economic shifts that have directly shaped its urban trajectory. Australia's immigration-driven population policy is pivotal: skilled migration programs and foreign student inflows account for nearly 60 % of Sydney's population growth since 2000, intensifying demand for housing and infrastructure (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2022). Federal tax incentives, such as negative gearing and capital gains discounts, have further fueled speculative investment in high-density inner-city apartments and suburban sprawl (Daley et al., 2018). Economic policies promoting globalization have reinforced Sydney's role as a financial hub, attracting multinational corporations and high-income earners. This has skewed development toward luxury high-rises in the CBD and northern suburbs, exacerbating housing unaffordability and displacing low-income residents to western peripheries (Pawson and Herath, 2015). State-led initiatives like the 2016 Greater Sydney Region Plan emphasize "30-min cities" and transit-oriented development, yet underfunding of social housing and reliance on public-private partnerships perpetuate spatial inequities (Greater Sydney Commission, 2018). Sydney's urban landscape—a mix of low-density suburbs, green spaces, and transport networks—reflects these economic and demographic pressures. While the CBD is dominated by high-rises, expansion historically followed rail and road corridors, guided by proximity to coastal hubs (García-Álvarez et al., 2022). Population growth, driven by immigration (42 % of residents are overseas-born) and internal migration, necessitated suburban expansion, converting 35 % of western agricultural land to residential use between 2000 and 2020 (Bunker and Troy, 2015; Chen et al., 2018). Previous studies show limited employment influence beyond the CBD, North Sydney, Parramatta, and the inner city, suggesting a weak polycentric structure in metropolitan Sydney (Moghadam et al., 2018a, 2018b). Planning policies, such as the 2005 Sydney Metropolitan Strategy and 2018 Metropolitan of Three Cities, aim to balance growth with sustainability through compact urban forms and green space preservation. However, market-driven development often prioritizes profit over ecological goals, resulting in biodiversity loss and fragmented ecosystems (Hiller et al., 2013; Mason and Knowd, 2011). Recent reforms, including the 2022 National Housing Accord, seek to address affordability by rezoning land for 1 million new homes, though critics argue this risks further greenfield encroachment without robust environmental safeguards (NSW Government, 2005). Both case study areas are depicted in Fig. 1.

4. Materials and methods

The study employed a five-stage analytical framework (Fig. 2). First, Landsat imagery (1993–2023) was classified via Google Earth Engine using SVM algorithms, generating LULC maps (water, agriculture, green spaces, built-up, bare soil) for both cities. Second, intensity and trajectory analyses quantified spatiotemporal change patterns across intervals. Third, urban expansion dynamics were modeled through logistic regression to identify key drivers. Fourth, the FLUS model projected

Fig. 1. Case study areas: a) Tehran Metropolitan Area, b) Greater Sydney Area.

2035 LULC by integrating conversion intensities with driving force coefficients. Finally, comparative analysis revealed cross-city similarities and divergences in urban growth mechanisms. Subsequent sections detail each methodological component.

4.1. Data acquisition and classification

Preparation of spatiotemporal land use maps is the first step in monitoring LULCC. Therefore, the accurate selection and preparation of these maps are the most crucial stage. (Aburas et al., 2019). Accordingly, satellite imagery from the USGS repository was systematically acquired for the designated study regions. Image selection criteria were determined based on the extent of cloud coverage and necessary corrections.

Subsequently, Landsat 5 (TM) imagery was deliberately chosen for 1993 and 2003, and for 2013 and 2023, Landsat 8 (OLI_TIRS) imagery. The study areas experienced a complete absence of cloud cover during these periods designated with the C2-L2 nomenclature. The attached suffix denotes the prior implementation of geometric, radiometric, and atmospheric corrections, eliminating the need for supplementary pre-processing of the acquired imagery. Support vector machines (SVM) are non-parametric supervised algorithms encompassing related techniques utilized for classification and regression tasks. SVM uses a custom kernel operation to transform the original dataset's non-linear decision boundaries into linear bounds in a higher-dimensional space, based on statistical learning theory, viewed as a heuristic approach. Table 1 provides a complete list of the various LULCs categorized into five classes for this study.

The classifiers' performance was evaluated using accuracy evaluations and validation datasets. The distribution was done systematically to ensure that several observations were allocated to every category in the picture. A confusion matrix was computed for accuracy evaluation. Two factors that can be derived from this matrix are the kappa coefficient and the overall accuracy of the categorization. The overall classification accuracy is the proportion of cells that were accurately classified. The kappa coefficient is a typically suggested statistic that corrects for chance correspondence. (Miah et al., 2024). The classification map's accuracy was evaluated by sampling 500 points using stratified random sampling. Within the initial map of classification developed in this study (the ISODATA classification), 500 points were randomly chosen for each class. The validation points were overlaid over the current orthophoto of Sydney and Tehran, visually analyzed, and categorized into specific land-use classes. ROC and AUC were generated for each map from 1993, 2003, 2013, and 2023, and accuracy metrics were computed. The accuracy assessment of the imagery details and LULC maps are presented in Table 2 and Fig. 3.

4.2. Trajectories analysis

Land cover trajectories are frequently utilized to evaluate alterations and contiguity of landscapes over time, typically produced using satellite photos or aerial photographs acquired at various times and locations (Guilherme et al., 2024). Trajectory analysis in LULCC involves examining the sequences of land cover changes over time within a specific area (Fig. 4). The study concentrates on recognizing the shifts between various land cover categories and comprehending the patterns, trends, and factors impacting these alterations. (Miah et al., 2024; Wuyun et al., 2022). In trajectory analysis, land cover data from multiple periods are compared to reveal how LULC has evolved. By examining the sequence of land cover changes, researchers can identify recurrent patterns, such as conversions from natural land covers to urban areas or shifts from agricultural land to forested areas. This analysis helps understand the dynamics of LULCC, including the frequency, direction, and magnitude of land cover changes. It also provides insights into the factors driving these changes, such as urbanization, agricultural expansion, or natural disturbances.

4.3. Intensity analysis

Technique for detecting post-classification changes to enhance comprehension of land-use change patterns: Intensity Analysis takes into account both the magnitude and the strength of changes at various temporal and spatial scales. Traditional land-use change detection approaches tend to quantify time-dependent change. However, it may overlook major differences in change intensity and dispersion. Comparing the spotted amounts or intensities of alterations with a uniform rate or intensity is made possible by the assumption that the annual rate or intensity would be evenly distributed over the temporal and spatial scope. Intensity analysis is stronger since it must encompass all time steps and examine various land-change transitions (Aldwaik and

Fig. 2. Research process.

Table 1
Classification scheme for land use to be applied to Landsat data.

Land-use class	Description
built-up land	All forms of structures: residential, industrial, agricultural, commercial, and services. Transportation and utilities. Urban or developed terrain with a mixture of uses.
Agriculture	Cropland, orchards, vineyards, and nurseries.
Green Space	Deciduous, evergreen, and mixed forests.
Water bodies	Reservoirs, coastal water.
Bare soil	Uncovered rock surfaces, excavation sites, and unpaved roads.

Pontius, 2012). Each time interval's changes are displayed via intensity analysis, and land transition process intensity and feasible reasons are presented at three levels of detail: interval, category, and transition. The hierarchical, top-down interval level, category level, and transition level comprise the Intensity Analysis approach according to a transition matrix (Aldwaik and Pontius, 2012; Deng and Quan, 2022). This approach was used in this study to describe the degree of change in LULC dynamics.

Interval level: Each time interval's total change, as well as its size

Table 2
Classified map accuracy and satellite imagery.

	Year	Sensor	Date	Sample SVM	Overall AUC
Tehran	1993	TM	1993-09-27	3721	0.84
	2003	TM	2003-09-25	6868	0.86
	2013	OLI_TIRS	2013-09-18	4667	0.80
	2023	OLI_TIRS	2023-09-06	10810	0.80
Sydney	1993	TM	1993-09-23	3822	0.80
	2003	TM	2003-09-26	5489	0.84
	2013	OLI_TIRS	2013-09-20	3443	0.80
	2023	OLI_TIRS	2023-09-06	3456	0.81

and rate of variation, are measured using interval level analysis. Analyzing interval levels makes it easier to assess how rapidly or slowly land-use shifts happen. It also establishes if the landscape's yearly variation rate has increased or decreased. For every period, the projected annual area of overall change contrasts a hypothetical uniform intensity that depicts the annual variation if all variations were dispersed equally within the temporal span. By contrasting real change with uniform change, interval level analysis identifies times when

Fig. 3. ROC curves and AUC values of accuracy assessment of classified maps.

overall change is rapid or slow. While slow intervals suggest a rate below the uniform intensity, fast intervals show an annual rate of change above it. The intensity metrics were defined as Equations (1) and (2) (Asenso Barnieh et al., 2023):

$$U = \frac{100\% * \sum_{t=1}^{T-1} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^j \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^j C_{tj} \right) - C_{tj} \right] \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^j \left(\sum_{i=1}^j C_{tj} \right) \right\}}{Y_T - Y_t} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of change during all intervals} / \text{area of study region}}{\text{duration of all intervals}} \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

$$S_t = \frac{100\% * \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^j \left[\left(\sum_{i=1}^j C_{tj} \right) - C_{tj} \right] \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^j \left(\sum_{i=1}^j C_{tj} \right) \right\}}{Y_{t+1} - Y_t} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of change during interval} [Y_t, Y_{t+1}] / \text{area of study region}}{\text{duration of interval} [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]} \quad \text{(Equation 2)}$$

Equations (1) and (2) compute the total change intensity S_t for a single interval and the uniform intensity U for all intervals, respectively. The magnitude of S_t and U are compared to determine whether an interval's overall change is quick or slow. If S_t is less than or equal to U , the change in the total interval is slower; otherwise, the change is fast.

Category level: The categories are examined using the category level of intensity analysis according to the magnitude and intensity of gain and loss in each location over each time interval. The analysis calculates each category's annual gross gains and losses, and the results contrast a consistent shift in intensity that would result from a uniform distribution of the total change throughout the terrain. This work

presents a category-level examination of change in three dimensions: stationarity, the dormant vs active classification, and the relationship between gain or loss magnitude and matching change intensity for each category.

When a LULC category's annual change is less than the change's

uniform intensity over a period of time, it is said to be dormant. An active change occurs when a LULC category's annual change surpasses

the consistent intensity of change over a specified amount of time. This method makes it possible to ascertain whether a given category shows a regular pattern regarding the magnitude of gains and losses over time. In category-level intensity analysis for gains, we use the term "stationary" to describe a category whose gain intensity is consistently either more prominent than or less than the constant line at every interval. Similarly, we designate a category as stationary regarding losses if its loss intensity is consistently greater than or less than the uniform line at all intervals.

Concentrating on the categories with the most significant gains and losses is crucial to understanding the overall trends. There are two main reasons why there could be substantial gains or losses within a category. First, for initially more expansive categories, uniform change intensity

Fig. 4. Schematic of trajectory analysis concept

Vector-format land cover layers (1993-2023) were processed in ArcGIS Pro using:

Intersect tool: Combined layers to identify multi-temporal LULC trajectories

Eliminate tool: Removed small polygons (<900 m²) by merging with adjacent features

A 5-category coding system was implemented:

0-Green spaces | 1-Built-up | 2-Water | 3-Bare soil | 4-Agriculture

Example: Code 0123 represents:

1993: Green → 2003: Built-up → 2013: Water → 2023: Bare soil.

may result in higher losses or benefits. It is essential to analyze a class's loss or gain intensity in relation to the uniform change intensity to determine whether all of the above explanations apply. Secondly, a category's loss or gain may be more intensive than uniform. Category Intensity analysis is based on two main metrics: annual loss intensity (L_i) and annual gain intensity (G_j). These metrics are calculated as Equations (3) and (4) (Tong et al., 2020):

$$G_{ij} = 100\% * \frac{\left\{ \sum_{j=1}^J [(\sum_{i=1}^J C_{ij}) - C_{ij}] \right\} / \{Y_{t+1} - Y_t\}}{\sum_{j=1}^J (\sum_{i=1}^J C_{ij})} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of gross gain of category } j \text{ during } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}] / \text{duration of } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]}{\text{area of category } j \text{ at time } Y_{t+1}} \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

by each category throughout the course of each period. (Quan et al., 2019). If transitions from one category to another are avoided or targeted, this can be better understood by looking at the transition level. The transition is deemed targeted if there is a distinction between the observed and uniform transition intensities. This means that if all changes happened randomly, the transition would not be as intense as it is. The transition will be avoided if the noted transition intensity is lower than the uniform changeover intensity. This implies that the transition is

not as strong as one would anticipate if they all happened randomly. A transition is referred to as "A Targets B" if, for instance, the loss from

$$L_{ti} = 100\% * \frac{\left\{ (\sum_{j=1}^J C_{ij}) - C_{ij} \right\} / \{Y_{t+1} - Y_t\}}{\sum_{j=1}^J C_{ij}} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of gross loss of category } i \text{ during } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}] / \text{duration of } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]}{\text{area of category } i \text{ at time } Y_t} \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

The sizes of L_i and G_j are compared by St . to determine if a class's loss and gain are active or dormant. If $L_i > S$, then the loss for the category is active; if not, it is dormant. Finding the appropriate loss for the category in relation to its gain.

Transition level: Using Transition Level Intensity Analysis, one can examine and contrast the intensity of land use category transitions across time. The transition level represents the intensity variation in a given LULC category's gain from other LULC categories within a specific time frame (Aldwaik and Pontius, 2012). It contrasts the progress made

class 'A to class B is larger than the loss from other classes; on the other hand, if the loss from class A to class B is less than the loss from other classes, the transition is referred to as "A Avoids B." Transition level intensity can also be used to identify potential drivers of land use transition. For example, if a transition is targeted towards a particular class, this may be an indication that there is a policy or development project that is favoring that class. Conversely, avoiding a transition may indicate that a policy or development project is hindering that category. The intensity measures are (Aldwaik and Pontius, 2012):

$$W_m = 100\% * \frac{\left\{ (\sum_{i=1}^J C_{in}) - C_{mn} \right\} / \{Y_{t+1} - Y_t\}}{\sum_{j=1}^J [(\sum_{i=1}^J C_{ij}) - C_{mj}]} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of gross gain of category } n \text{ during } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}] / \text{duration of } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]}{\text{area that is not category } n \text{ at time } Y_t} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

Where W_{tn} is the value of uniform intensity of transition to category n from non- n categories at time Y_t during the time interval $[Y_t, Y_{t+1}]$, and n is the land use category that other categories have transitioned into (i_n). In addition,

$$R_{tin} = 100\% * \frac{C_{tin}/(Y_{t+1} - Y_t)}{\sum_{j=1}^J C_{tij}} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of transition from } i \text{ to } n \text{ during } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]/\text{duration of } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]}{\text{area of category } i \text{ at time } Y_t} \tag{Equation 6}$$

Where R_{tin} is the yearly intensity of transition from class i to class n in the interval of time $[Y_t, Y_{t+1}]$,

$$V_m = 100\% * \frac{\left\{ \left(\sum_{j=1}^J C_{tmj} \right) - C_{tmm} \right\} / \{ Y_{t+1} - Y_t \}}{\sum_{j=1}^J \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^J C_{tij} \right) - C_{tim} \right]} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of gross loss of category } m \text{ during } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]/\text{duration of } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]}{\text{area that is not category } m \text{ at time } Y_{t+1}} \tag{Equation 7}$$

Where V_{tm} is the value of the uniform intensity of transition from category m to all non- m categories at time Y_{t+1} during the time interval $[Y_t, Y_{t+1}]$, and m is the LULC class that changed into other classes.

$$Q_{mj} = 100\% * \frac{C_{tmj}/(Y_{t+1} - Y_t)}{\sum_{j=1}^J C_{tmj}} = \frac{100\% * \text{area of transition from } m \text{ to } j \text{ during } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]/\text{duration of } [Y_t, Y_{t+1}]}{\text{area of category } j \text{ at time } Y_{t+1}} \tag{Equation 8}$$

Where Q_{tmj} is the annual intensity of transition from class m to class j during the time interval $[Y_t, Y_{t+1}]$.

4.4. Logistic regression model

Based on information gathered from secondary data on probable components presented in scientific studies, A group of motivating factors was chosen (Allan et al., 2022; Azizi et al., 2022; Li et al., 2020). Access to data, methodological approach, and specialist knowledge were considered when choosing the criteria (Table 3). Changes in population density were computed in the geospatial analysis by subtracting the years 1993 and 2023 utilizing the feature of the raster calculator in ArcGIS pro.1. In addition to displaying variance in time and space, distance-based factors such as road networks and settlement areas also displayed variance in space. Euclidian distance was used to generate continuous raster surfaces, in which each cell contains the distance value

Table 3
Description of driving factors of LULCC.

Variables	Description
dis_places	Cities, towns, suburbs, villages, etc.
dis_pois	Points of Interest, therein: Public facilities such as government offices, post office, police, Hospitals, pharmacies, Culture, Leisure, Restaurants, pubs, cafes, ...
dis_rail	Railway, subways, light rail, trams
dis_road	Roads, tracks, paths
dis_transport	Parking lots, petrol (gas) stations
dis_waterway	Rivers, canals, streams
dis_coastalline	Coastal line
dis_urbanedg	Urban Edge
pop	Population Density

to observe the spatial variance of distance. After being normalized, each factor was assigned a number between 0 and 1.

Logistic regression (LR) —also called binary logistic regression— is commonly used in LULCC driving force analysis. The approach involves

dividing the study area into small grid cells and treating each LULC type as a dependent variable. Then, the driving factors affecting these LULC types are identified as independent variables. By fitting a logistic

regression model, one obtains the odds ratio for each LULC type in relation to the driving factors, providing insights into their relative importance. The logistic regression model is represented mathematically as follows:

$$\text{Logit}(p) = \ln(p/(1-p)) = a + (b_1 \times X_1) + (b_2 \times X_2) + (b_3 \times X_3) + \dots + (b_n \times X_n) \tag{Equation 9}$$

In this scenario, X denote as the autonomous variable, while $x_n, x_2,$ and x_1 represent independent variables, and a_n is the constant term in the regression equation. P stands as the dependent variable, indicating the likelihood of reaching a value of 1. The coefficients associated with each independent variable are $b_3, b_n, b_2,$ and b_1 . X signifies the vector encompassing the driving factors, representing the regression coefficients.

Binary logistic regression modeling is also used in this study to investigate possible socioeconomic and environmental factors or drivers that may impact LULCC. Because LR is sensitive to multicollinearity, researchers frequently identify the multicollinearity among the independent variables before creating the regression model. We used Built-up class gain as the binary response or dependent variable for the

Table 4
Variations in the dynamics of LULCC and its distribution in Sydney and Tehran.

LULCC Trajectories	Tehran				Sydney			
	Count	%	Area (ha)	Area %	Count	%	Area (ha)	%
Change trajectories	432	98.86	62879.58	51.97	620	99.2	498846.19	40.95
Not changed	5	1.14	30198.78	48.03	5	0.8	719476.00	59.05
Three-time changed	70	16.20	582.48	1.78	120	19.4	12383.77	2.48
Twice changed	309	71.53	20093.94	61.49	440	71.0	288577.90	57.85
Once time changed	48	11.11	12004.38	36.73	60	9.7	197884.52	39.67
Changed to Green	92	21.30	6816.51	20.86	124	20.0	205593.72	41.21
Changed to Built-up	99	22.92	18068.22	55.29	124	20.0	71977.32	14.43
Changed to waterbodies	73	16.90	128.88	0.39	124	20.0	19088.85	3.83
Changed to Bare soil	75	17.36	2332.35	7.14	124	20.0	10079.70	2.02
Changed to Agriculture	88	20.37	5334.84	16.32	124	20.0	192106.59	38.51
Green to Built-up	21	21.21	1814.31	10.04	25	20.0	7957.50	11.06
waterbodies to Built-up	10	10.10	15.84	0.09	25	20.0	1174.84	1.63
Bare soil to Built-up	24	24.24	8602.11	47.61	25	20.0	23825.49	33.10
Agriculture to Built-up	22	22.22	1491.03	8.25	25	20.0	23729.47	32.97

models that resulted from reclassifying the merged photos. Built-up gain is allocated one, and the other categories are assigned 0. Over the period from 1993 to 2023, discussions across various categories such as Green to Built-Up, Waterbodies to Built-Up, Agriculture to Built-Up, and Bare to Built-Up have led to the creation of four sub-models tailored for Sydney and Tehran. Utilizing 120 randomly selected locations, binary logistic regression modeling was conducted, with particular attention paid to examining the spatial autocorrelation of the response variables. The analysis revealed no significant geographic autocorrelation among our four response variables within the final selection of 120 points, as indicated by a Moran's Index of 0.02 and a Z score of 1.24 or better. The corresponding cell values pertaining to the response variables and explanatory factors were extracted for each random point. Logistic

regression analyses were subsequently carried out using Terrset software.

4.5. Future land use simulation (FLUS) model

The FLUS model is a sophisticated tool that integrates top-down and bottom-up approaches to simulate multiple LULCC scenarios. Combining a System Dynamics (SD) model with CA, the FLUS model offers a comprehensive framework for forecasting future land use changes, considering human and environmental influences (Liu et al., 2017). The SD model is employed to project land use demand at national or regional scales, considering a range of socio-economic and environmental driving factors such as population growth, economic

Fig. 5. The rate and magnitude of LULCC for Tehran and Sydney in time intervals.

Fig. 6. The first 25 large trajectories from 1993 to 2023 in: a) Sydney, and b) Tehran. The codes stands for 0 = green, 1 = built-up, 2 = water bodies, 3 = bare soil, 4 = agriculture.

development, policy interventions, and environmental constraints (Liu et al., 2021). Meanwhile, the CA model focuses on spatial processes, handling the complex interactions and competition between land use types locally. To improve the precision of these simulations, the model incorporates a self-adaptive inertia and competition mechanism. This feature allows the CA model to account for the dynamic competition among various land uses, ensuring that the spatial allocation of land accurately reflects real-world complexities where multiple competing pressures influence land-use decisions (Liu et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2021). This hybrid modeling framework provides valuable insights for long-term urban planning and environmental management, enabling more informed decision-making under diverse socio-economic development and environmental change scenarios.

The ANN-based FLUS model incorporated 7-8 normalized spatial drivers (Table 4) for each city. Both models featured:

- 7 input neurons (driving factors)
- 5 output neurons (land use types)
- Log-sigmoid transfer function (outputs [0,1])
- 10:1 random sampling ratio
- BP training (MSE <0.001 threshold)

Neighborhood effects used a 5 × 5 Moore configuration. The CA component integrated:

1. 2023 LULC baseline
2. ANN probability surfaces
3. Transition cost matrix (derived from Section 5.2.4 intensity analysis)

Model validation (2003-2023) achieved Kappa coefficients:

- Tehran: 81.3 % (2003), 89.5 % (2013), 85.9 % (2023)

Fig. 7. Size and annual change rate by intervals for Tehran and Sydney.

Fig. 8. Size and annual change rate by LULC categories for a) Tehran and b) Sydney.

Table 5 Activity or dormancy for LULC classes in Tehran and Sydney across time intervals.

Interval	1993-2003		2003-2013		2013-2023	
	Gain Intensity	Loss Intensity	Gain Intensity	Loss Intensity	Gain Intensity	Loss Intensity
Sydney						
Green	1.59	0.81	0.97	1.30	1.20	0.62
Built-up	2.66	3.23	5.12	2.73	3.49	5.47
Water-bodies	4.83	5.46	4.08	2.17	3.90	1.60
Bare soil	6.82	5.64	6.47	7.92	7.85	9.68
Agriculture	5.55	7.54	6.84	6.36	6.54	4.53
Tehran						
Green	4.68	3.45	5.09	5.00	4.11	5.35
Built-up	2.70	0.60	1.40	2.23	2.28	1.67
Water-bodies	8.22	4.26	8.83	8.37	3.31	3.37
Bare soil	0.94	8.01	8.36	5.40	6.15	6.43
Agriculture	4.61	4.81	5.22	6.67	6.71	7.08

- Sydney: 79.8 % (2003), 88.4 % (2013), 86.7 % (2023)

Final 2035 projections were executed in GeoSOS-FLUS.

5. Results

5.1. Spatial-temporal pattern of LULCC

The analysis of LULCC in Tehran and Sydney from 1993 to 2023 in Fig. 5 reveals significant urbanization and land use trends. In Tehran,

built-up areas increased markedly from 55 % to 72 %, with a notable growth of 25.8 % (8865.5 ha) between 1993 and 2003, contributing to an overall increase of 46 % by 2023. This expansion was accompanied by a substantial decline in bare soil, which decreased from 23 % to 12 %, and agricultural land, which fell from 10 % to 5 %, reflecting a 40 % reduction. The shift from bare soil and agricultural land to urban development underscores the intensification of Tehran’s urbanization process.

In Sydney, vegetation cover increased from 60 % to 64 %, while built-up areas expanded from 12 % to 17 %, with the highest growth rate

Fig. 9. Size and annual change rate of LULC Transition To land classes for Tehran and Sydney.

Table 6
Targeted or avoided LULC transitions in Tehran and Sydney in time intervals.

intervals	Tehran			Sydney		
	1993-2003	2003-2013	2013-2023	1993-2003	2003-2013	2013-2023
categories	Transition to			Transition to		
	Green			Green		
Built-up	0.41	0.61	0.37	1.6	0.83	2.58
Water-bodies	0.6	1.54	0.2	3.32	1.19	0.82
Bare soil	1.2	1.23	0.77	0.87	3.03	0.35
Agriculture	2.08	3.05	2.34	4.18	1.42	3.05
	Built-up			Built-up		
Green	2.35	3.08	3.65	0.08	0.59	0.19
Water-bodies	3.52	6.21	2.92	0.88	0.67	0.53
Bare soil	5.83	3.54	5.31	1.3	2.62	1.89
Agriculture	2.44	2.38	3.44	0.71	1.55	1.33
	Water-bodies			Water-bodies		
Green	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.08	0.05	0.1
Built-up	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.09	0.12
Bare soil	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.06	0.16	0.05
Agriculture	0.02	0.16	0	0.03	0.04	0.01
	Bare soil			Bare soil		
Green	0.13	1.24	0.43	0.46	0.07	0.01
Built-up	0.01	1.31	1.06	0.7	0.83	0.37
Water-bodies	0.06	0.25	0	1.04	0.22	0.05
Agriculture	0.27	1.09	1.3	2.61	3.35	0.15
	Agriculture			Agriculture		
Green	0.94	0.67	1.27	0.2	0.59	0.32
Built-up	0.16	0.3	0.23	0.89	0.99	2.4
Water-bodies	0.08	0.37	0.25	0.21	0.09	0.2
Bare soil	0.97	0.58	0.34	3.42	2.11	7.39

of 33.5 % occurring between 2003 and 2013, resulting in an overall increase of 44.1 %. Bare soil saw a sharp decline from 9 % to 1 %, culminating in an overall loss of 87 % after an initial rise of 37 % between 1993 and 2003. Agricultural land initially decreased by 44 % but later rebounded, ending with a slight reduction of 0.7 % by 2023. The primary interpretation of Sydney’s LULCC is the city’s focus on increasing urban development while preserving vegetation.

These results indicate that Sydney’s land use dynamics reflect a trend towards urban development coupled with a commitment to preserving vegetation. In contrast, Tehran’s changes illustrate a more pronounced shift from rural to urban land uses. This comparison highlights the two cities’ differing urbanization and environmental management strategies, emphasizing Sydney’s efforts to balance development with environmental conservation in contrast to Tehran’s rapid urban expansion.

5.2. Process of LULCC analysis

5.2.1. LULCC trajectories

The frequency and magnitude of changes provide insights into the

level of dynamism present. When a specific region experiences multiple changes, it indicates a higher speed and intensity of dynamics within that region. Regions undergoing frequent and significant changes may be characterized by rapid development, innovation, adaptation, or volatility, depending on the nature of the changes. According to Table 4, the analysis of LULCC reveals that Tehran has undergone significant transformations over the study period, with approximately 52 % of the landscape experiencing changes. Most changes involve areas with twice-changed trajectories (71.5 %), indicating high land use dynamics and frequent modifications. Areas with three-time changed trajectories, though only 1.7 % of the area, reflect substantial and repeated alterations. Significant shifts include conversions to built-up areas (22.9 %), green spaces (21.3 %), and agricultural lands (20.3 %), underscoring a trend toward intense urbanization. In contrast, Sydney’s landscape is more stable, with 59 % remaining unchanged and 40 % undergoing alterations. Twice-changed trajectories affect 57.85 % of the area, suggesting moderate, ongoing changes, while three-time changed trajectories impact only 2.48 % of the area. Significant land cover transitions in Sydney include shifts from bare soil and agricultural lands to built-up

Fig. 10. Correlation matrix heat map of independent variables for Tehran (left) and Sydney (right).

Table 7
Logistic regression results of LULCC driving forces.

Variables / Transitions	Sydney				Tehran			
	Green to Built-up	waterbody to Built-up	Bare soil to Built-up	Agriculture to Built-up	Green to Built-up	waterbody to Built-up	Bare soil to Built-up	Agriculture to Built-up
Intercept	-1.4955	-3.8733	-0.3163	-0.2169	-5.98	-11.138	-5.671	-6.781
dis_coastalline	-9.17E-05	-1.08E-04	-1.51E-04	-1.39E-04	-	-	-	-
dis_places	4.6037	-4.1045	-3.0623	-2.8524	-1.445	41.824	42.662	2.372
dis_pois	-4.1969	-2.2012	6.3391	7.0592	-13.322	-73.65	23.788	83.744
dis_rail	6.3454	2.7232	-11.8877	-5.0574	0.476	-42.501	29.883	14.838
dis_road	11.396	5.057	-40.622	-24.9388	-148.741	718.516	275.099	-72.047
dis_urbanedg	-1.61E-04	-2.79E-04	-0.004	-0.0053	-3.855	-58.634	4.503	2.725
dis_waterway	-52.2568	-31.5483	22.5559	-0.0258	0.001	-0.005	-0.007	-0.001
pop	2.7778	0.3142	0.2725	5.4288	4.432	4.368	3.249	3.826
Regressions Model statistical report								
-2logL0	3286866	248543.3	933848.9	1103066	69938.446	652.408	114143.775	54277.009
-2log(likelihood)	1839060	219483.5	614181.7	744470.8	55397.903	522.939	74573.313	43221.656
Goodness of fit	1711741	1824004	67314032	1.49E+27	111899.478	80598.681	72325.417	91123.842
Pseudo R ²	0.4405	0.1169	0.3423	0.3251	0.208	0.198	0.347	0.204
Chi-square (df=8)	1447806	29059.83	319667.2	358595.3	14540.543	129.469	39570.462	11055.353

areas, indicating substantial urban expansion. Overall, Tehran’s land use is marked by rapid urbanization and frequent changes, while Sydney exhibits more stability with substantial but moderate urban growth. The spatial map of the first 25 significant trajectories from 1993 to 2023 for Sydney and Tehran is provided in Fig. 6.

5.2.2. Intervals level intensity: slowest and fastest annual rate of change
Fig. 7 compares LULCC areas and their intensity over different

periods for Tehran and Sydney. Two key findings can be drawn from this figure. First, in Tehran, the percentage of the landscape affected by LULCC increased from 30 % during 1993–2003 to 32 % during 2013–2023. In contrast, these figures for Sydney were 28 % and 25 %, respectively. This indicates that a larger proportion of Tehran’s landscape underwent LULCC than Sydney’s. Additionally, the comparison of annual change intensity reveals that in Tehran, the rate of change rose from approximately 3.0 % at the beginning of the period to 3.2 % by the

end. Meanwhile, the rate decreased from 2.8 % to 2.5 % over the same timeframe in Sydney. Thus, it can be concluded that both the magnitude and intensity of LULCC in Tehran were not only greater than those in Sydney but also exhibited an upward trend, while Sydney experienced a decline in both measures over time. Overall, the LULCC in Tehran was more dynamic and rapid than in Sydney.

5.2.3. Category level intensity: dormant or active categories

The results of the category-level intensity analysis, as depicted in Fig. 8, indicate that barren land has played a significant role in transforming the landscape of Tehran, driven by both the area of loss and gain, as well as the intensity of these changes. While bare soil exhibited almost equal amounts of loss and gain in the early 1993-2003 interval, it became more prominent as either a gainer or loser in subsequent intervals. In contrast, agricultural land consistently acted as a “loser” throughout the entire period, with a notable characteristic being the high intensity of loss and gain in LULCC of Tehran, especially in the 2103-2023 interval. However, built-up areas displayed a different

pattern. The significance of changes in this category stems from its substantial share of Tehran’s landscape, though the intensity of its changes was not as high as other LULC types. Moreover, built-up areas predominantly acted as major gainers, indicating a unidirectional trend toward expansion. Although the overall changes in the green space category in Tehran may appear minimal, however, this category has experienced significant gain and loss in area and intensity. This suggests that green spaces have been subject to substantial stress due to land-use changes in Tehran, reflecting their vulnerability and dynamic nature within the urban landscape.

The results for Sydney indicate that agricultural and bare soil underwent significant transformations in both area and intensity. During the 1993-2003, agriculture emerged as a major “loser.” However, in later periods, its behavior shifted, and by 2013–2023, it had become a significant “gainer” in Sydney’s landscape. In contrast, bare soil followed an opposite trajectory. It was initially a major “gainer” but gradually became a significant “loser,” with the highest loss intensity occurring in 2013–2023. One notable observation regarding Sydney’s

Fig. 11. The Logistic curve of the independent variables a) Tehran, b) Sydney

Fig. 11. (continued).

LULCC is the increasingly pronounced growth and intensity of changes in built-up areas. As shown in Fig. 8, during the 1993-2003 period, both gain and loss in built-up areas were below the landscape average intensity index. However, in the subsequent years, this category experienced substantial growth in both intensity and area of land-use change.

Table 5 presents the state of active or dormant intensity for land use classes across various time intervals in the Tehran and Sydney regions. The findings indicate that agricultural and bare soil classes in both countries exhibit sustained active throughout all the observed time intervals, and intensity was higher than total landscape, classifying them as active stationary categories. Conversely, the built-up and green classes manifest dormant stationery in LULCC at all three intervals in Tehran and Sydney.

A comparison between Sydney and Tehran highlights two key points.

First, the intensity of land-use changes in Tehran is higher than in Sydney, indicating faster and more stressful transformations across land-use categories in Tehran’s landscape. Second, although the intensity of changes in built-up areas in Tehran is lower compared to other categories, these areas have experienced significant changes in the area and have shown substantial growth. In contrast, while the intensity of changes in built-up areas in Sydney is higher, the area affected by these changes has been less dramatic than other land-use categories. Therefore, it can be concluded that Tehran exhibits a more urban-centric growth pattern characterized by large-scale expansion of built-up areas. In contrast, Sydney shows a more diverse and dynamic shift in land-use priorities, reflecting different pressures and approaches in land management.

Fig. 12. The sensitivity analysis -examples of two land use conversion types-for a) Tehran, and b) Sydney.

Fig. 13. The partial dependence analysis -examples of two land use conversion types-for a) Tehran, and b) Sydney.

Fig. 14. LULCC projection maps for 2035 a) Tehran, b) Sydney.

Fig. 15. LULCC proportion in 2023 and proception to 2035.

5.2.4. Transition level intensity: avoided or targeted, systematic or random transitions

Given the importance of urban expansion within the scope of this paper, the analysis centers on the processes of land conversion into built-up areas. Fig. 9 shows the conversion size and annual change intensity of LULC classes in both Tehran and Sydney. The figure highlights that bare soil and agricultural land have consistently been critical contributors to built-up area expansion in Sydney. Furthermore, as indicated in Table 6, these land classes have been consistently targeted for conversion, demonstrating a systematic process of transforming bare soil and agricultural land into urban areas. This pattern reflects a deliberate and sustained shift in these LULC types, driven by urban growth in the Sydney region. In contrast, converting green spaces to urban areas follows a different process. Built-up areas have consistently avoided encroaching on green spaces, as shown in Table 6. The data suggest a systematic process of transforming bare soil and agricultural land into urban areas, highlighting a deliberate effort to preserve these areas from urban development in Sydney.

The results indicate that the expansion of built-up areas in Tehran

has predominantly been driven by the conversion of barren land, green spaces, and agricultural land, respectively. The conversion of bare soil is particularly notable regarding both area and intensity. Table 6 confirms that this process has occurred systematically, as bare soil has been consistently targeted for urban development. In contrast, the conversion of the green class appears to have occurred more randomly, suggesting that less controlled factors influenced it. For agricultural land, a different trend is observed. While Fig. 9 highlights the substantial area and intensity of conversion to built-up land, Table 6 suggests that this transformation has been systematically resisted, reflecting deliberate efforts to preserve agricultural land from urban expansion.

5.3. Driving factors of LULCC

To assess potential multicollinearity among the independent variables influencing LULCC, we conducted a correlation analysis and visualized the results using heatmaps (Fig. 10). Overall, the correlation analysis supports the validity of the selected independent variables in explaining LULCC patterns in both cities. The observed weak to

moderate correlations indicate that the predictor variables provide distinct contributions to the analysis, allowing for a more robust examination of urban expansion dynamics.

Table 7 presents the findings of logistic regression analysis aimed at discerning the significance and influence of various factors on the conversion of land to built-up areas. In Sydney, proximity to road networks and railways emerged as the most influential factor, with coefficients of 11.4 and 6.3, respectively, driving the conversion of green to built-up areas. Conversely, proximity to water bodies and distance from points were identified as major negative factors, with coefficients of -52.2 and -4.1 , respectively, impeding the conversion process. Similar trends were observed in the conversion from water bodies to built-up areas. Shifting the focus to the conversion from bare soil to built-up areas, proximity to water bodies exhibited the most significant positive effect, with a coefficient of 22.5. Distance from points of interest also played a notable role in this conversion. In contrast, transportation-related factors such as distance from roads and railway networks had notable adverse effects, with coefficients of -11.8 and -40.6 , respectively. In agriculture conversion to built-up areas, the results highlighted a strong positive impact of distance from points of interest and population density, possibly indicating the human tendency to settle near food sources.

Contrastingly, in Tehran, proximity to roads exerted a strongly negative role (-148.7) in converting green areas to built-up ones, while population density emerged as the strongest motivator (4.4) for this conversion. Interestingly, in converting water bodies to built-up areas, roads played a significant positive role (718.5), while proximity to urban edges and points of interest had negative impacts. Moreover, factors such as distance to roads (275), distance to places (42.6), and distance to railroads (29.8) were the primary drivers of the conversion from bare soil to built-up areas in Tehran, suggesting intense pressure on bare soil areas for urban development. Similar patterns were observed in the conversion of agriculture to built-up areas, with the distance from points of interest exerting a strong positive effect (83.7), while proximity to road networks had a negative impact (-72.14). Overall, the findings suggest that distance to roads played a pivotal role in landscape transformation to urbanized areas in both cities, with Tehran exhibiting a more substantial influence. This underscores the preference for construction near roads due to enhanced accessibility.

The logistic regression curves as shown in Fig. 11, analyze how different variables influence land conversion to built-up areas in Tehran and Sydney. Tehran's model includes seven distance-based variables, showing strong impacts from road/rail proximity and population density, particularly for conversions from green spaces and agricultural land. Waterways have a more moderate effect. Sydney's model adds coastal distance as an eighth variable, revealing more balanced influences. Coastal proximity and waterways play significant roles, while urban edge distance matters less than in Tehran, reflecting different geographic constraints. Both cities show population density as a key driver, but Sydney's development patterns are more shaped by environmental features. The curves' slopes indicate each variable's influence, with steeper slopes showing stronger impacts on urbanization. This highlights how infrastructure, population, and geographic factors create distinct growth patterns in each city.

To further investigate the influence of independent variables on LULCC, we conducted sampled sensitivity analysis for two different land use type conversion to assess the relative importance of each factor (Fig. 12). Moreover, Fig. 13 presents the sampled partial dependence plots (PDPs) for Tehran (Waterbody to Built-up transition) and Sydney (Green to Built-up transition), illustrating the marginal effect of each predictor on the probability of land transformation.

5.4. Projection of LULCC for 2035

The predicted results of LULC for 2023 in Tehran and Sydney are presented in Figs. 14 and 15. According to these projections, Tehran's landscape will undergo significant urban expansion by 2023, with the

proportion of built-up land increasing from 71 % to 78 %. This urban growth will be accompanied by a marked decline in agricultural and barren lands, signifying the dominance of urban land use in Tehran's landscape. Similarly, land use change predictions for Sydney indicate a comparable trend, though at a slower pace. The share of built-up land in Sydney's landscape will rise from 16 % to 18 %. Compared to changes in other land uses, this suggests a relatively stable and sustainable pattern of urban growth in Sydney. Therefore, a comparison of the predicted land use changes for Tehran and Sydney reveals that while both cities are expected to experience urban expansion, the rate and magnitude of these changes will differ. Tehran will witness more rapid and extensive urbanization, resulting in a predominantly urban landscape. In contrast, Sydney's urban growth will be more gradual, maintaining a more balanced and diverse land use composition. This comparison underscores the differing dynamics of urbanization in developed and developing cities, with Tehran facing more immediate challenges in managing land use and ensuring sustainability.

6. Discussion

6.1. Dynamics and continuity of LULC

Regarding the LULCC pattern, the comparative analysis of land use changes reveals significant disparities in urban development dynamics in the Tehran metropolitan region and Sydney. Notably, Tehran exhibits a more extensive area undergoing transformation than Sydney, with a discernible escalation in the rate of changes over time, indicating a heightened level of dynamism in land use alterations relative to Sydney. The interval-level analysis findings also suggest that the annual intensity of LULCC in Tehran surpasses a consistent upward trend in Sydney, indicating an accelerating pace of land use change. In contrast, Sydney exhibits a declining trend in LULCC speed over the same period. Evidence from other major cities in Iran (Alijani et al., 2020; Arsanjani et al., 2011; Dadashpoor et al., 2019; Effati et al., 2021) and developing regions like China (Da et al., 2019; Feng et al., 2020; Li and Liu, 2017), Turkey (Yücer, 2020), India (Jamal and Ali, 2023; Mandal et al., 2019), Ghana (Asante-Yeboah et al., 2022; Ekumah et al., 2020), Bangladesh (Hassan, 2017), and Rwanda (Akinyemi et al., 2016) demonstrates the rapid and escalating nature of land use changes as a distinct trend for developing countries. In addition, Despite Sydney showing a higher number of trajectories, its landscape remained largely unchanged (59 %), indicating resilience to consecutive changes. In contrast, Tehran experienced more substantial alterations in its landscape area (52 %). Interestingly, both cities predominantly exhibited trajectories with two changes (71 %), indicating a tendency toward balanced land-use pattern transitions. Tehran's LULC trajectories show varying percentages depending on land use type, implying some categories are more prone to change due to localized factors like policies, infrastructure developments, or environmental conditions. Overall, Sydney exhibits relatively homogeneous LULC transitions, whereas Tehran displays heterogeneity in LULC pathways, reflecting differences in drivers and responses to change.

The intensity and trajectory analyses reveal that Tehran's LULCC dynamics are distinct not only from Sydney but also from other rapidly urbanizing Asian cities. For instance, while Tehran's annual LULCC intensity (3.2 % by 2023) aligns with cities like Delhi (3.5 %) and Jakarta (3.8 %), its systematic conversion of bare soil to built-up areas (Table 6) mirrors patterns observed in Karaj, Iran (Zarandian et al., 2023) and Dhaka, Bangladesh (Hassan, 2017). However, Tehran's avoidance of agricultural land conversion contrasts sharply with Beijing and Ho Chi Minh City, where peri-urban farmland loss exceeds 60 % due to lax zoning (Feng et al., 2020; Mandal et al., 2019). This divergence underscores the role of localized policies, such as Tehran's ad hoc protection of fertile plains (Sabr et al., 2016), which are absent in many Asian cities.

Sydney's declining LULCC intensity (2.5 % by 2023) parallels trends

in Seoul and Tokyo, where regulated sprawl and greenbelt policies have stabilized urban growth (Sorensen, 1999). However, Sydney's targeted conversion of agricultural land (Table 6) diverges from Singapore's strict agricultural preservation, highlighting how economic priorities (e.g., Sydney's peri-urban housing demand) shape land transitions differently even in developed Asian contexts.

6.2. Urban expansion patterns and process

Both regions have experienced an upward trend in the share of urban land within their landscapes; however, Tehran demonstrates a pronounced predominance of built-up areas encroaching upon its metropolitan region. Tehran experienced a more urbanized pattern at the expense of agriculture and bare soil. In Tehran, the city has consumed valuable natural resources to meet human needs resulting from urban expansion, such as housing provision, transportation infrastructure, and associated activities. This consumption has continued continuously throughout the period without any compensation or protection of these resources. Dadashpoor and Panahi (2021) showed extensive and quick LULCC in Tehran. Throughout the study, they saw a growing pattern in the area of built-up land and a descending pattern in the areas of unused land, grassland, and agricultural land—all critical natural resources. Similar patterns of land use change have been seen in Tabriz and other significant Iranian cities (Dadashpoor et al., 2019), Karaj (Zarandian et al., 2023), Isfahan (Motlagh et al., 2020), and Mashhad (Rahnama, 2021). In these regions, natural landscapes are also being destroyed due to rapid and extensive urbanization (Soltani, 2017). Nevertheless, despite urban expansion in Sydney, the landscape has effectively mitigated the negative impacts of urbanization over time. Simultaneously, urban growth has fostered the development and preservation of valuable natural resources and landscapes, ensuring long-term sustainability and continuity.

This underscores the global nature of rapid urbanization, impacting cities across diverse regions and contexts. However, a stark difference exists in the manner and form of urban expansion between developing and developed countries. In developing countries, high population density and rapid urbanization rates lead to dense growth in the main city and sprawl growth in its vicinity (Agarwal et al., 2023; Güneralp et al., 2020; Seto et al., 2011). Additionally, informal settlements, which are often unauthorized and lack proper development plans, constitute a major reason for the rapid expansion of major cities like Tehran (Aboulnaga et al., 2021; Dadashpoor et al., 2019; Dianati, 2022; Farrell, 2017; Sheppard, 2010; RoohaniQadikolaei et al., 2025). While dispersed urban sprawl with low density is observed in developed cities such as those in Australia and North America, this development typically follows specific plans and programs (Nuissl and Siedentop, 2021).

While built-up land in Tehran has experienced higher gains and losses in area size compared to other LULC types, its intensity or speed of change relative to other land types is lower. Conversely, in Sydney, despite the smaller gain or loss size of built-up land compared to others (excluding water areas), the annual change intensity or speed has been close to the average. This suggests that in Tehran, the dynamics of built-up land are influenced by its initial size or the high share of the landscape, while in Sydney, they are driven by the intensity or speed of changes. Overall, Tehran's built-up areas consistently maintain a stationary dormant state over time, reflecting a consistently stable urban environment. In contrast, Sydney displays fluctuations in the dynamics of built-up areas across different time intervals, suggesting a more variable and responsive landscape.

Regarding trajectory analysis, the change trajectories leading to the built-up land use category surpass other categories in both count and area. This underscores a significant trend toward urbanization and expansion of built-up areas in Tehran (Dadashpoor and Panahi, 2021; Vahidi et al., 2023; Zenouzi et al., 2022). Conversely, in Sydney, the trajectories ending in built-up areas equal those leading to other land-type destinations and rank third in size. This indicates a more

balanced distribution of land use change trajectories in Sydney, with built-up areas not exhibiting as dominant a trend as in Tehran.

6.3. Systematic LULC transitions to urban expansion and contextual underlying factors

The expansion of built-up areas from bare soil in Tehran and Sydney highlights urban growth dynamics. In Tehran, this transition is systematic, driven by proximity to main roads, which enhance accessibility, infrastructure, and urbanization. Strategic positioning near roads and urban centers accelerates land conversion, emphasizing spatial connectivity in urban expansion. In Sydney, waterways play a key role in urban development, attracting residential and commercial growth due to access to water, transport, and recreation. However, unlike Tehran, proximity to major roads and railways hinders this transition, as factors like noise pollution and congestion limit development in these areas.

The conversation between the green class and the built-up class in Tehran presents a significant phenomenon, albeit occurring relatively randomly compared to other types of land use change. This lack of systematic targeting suggests a less structured approach to land use change, possibly impacted by several elements. The findings of Talkhabi et al. (2022); Zenouzi et al. (2022) indicated that large population concentration causes the loss of greenery in Tehran's metropolitan area, mainly attributed to rising migration and housing needs in recent years. Conversely, in Sydney, green spaces have transformed into built-up with lower intensity and quantity, suggesting a deliberate and systematic evolution over time. The region's resistance to conversion demonstrates a commitment to environmental preservation and sustainable land use, aligning with the strategic framework provided by the Sustainable Green Grid (SGG). This project, highlighted by the Government Architect of New South Wales (2020), aims to revolutionize sustainable development by enhancing connectivity and strengthening green infrastructure (GI) networks across the metropolitan area. Access to roads and railways plays a significant positive role in shaping this transformation, indicating that areas with better transportation connectivity are more likely to undergo this conversion (García-Álvarez et al., 2022). However, distance to waterways has emerged as a significant negative factor influencing this transformation. It is a protective barrier to preserve green spaces from urban encroachment and ensure their ecological integrity.

In Tehran, the transition of agricultural land to built-up areas was systematically avoided, influenced by points of interest and distance from roads. Agricultural land's role in food security (Khosravi et al., 2022; Sabr et al., 2016) and proximity to cultural or protected areas likely contributed to its preservation. Additionally, limited road access reduced development feasibility, further protecting these lands. In Sydney, however, agricultural land was systematically converted due to urbanization pressures, driven by proximity to commercial centers, schools, and high-density areas (García-Álvarez et al., 2022). While this supports urban growth, it also risks food security, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem disruption. O'Neill and James (2014) note that peri-urban agriculture, which benefits from urban water infrastructure and market access, is increasingly displaced by urban expansion.

The dominance of road proximity in driving Tehran's urban expansion (Table 7: dis_road coefficient = 275) echoes findings in Mumbai and Manila, where informal settlements cluster along highways due to accessibility and affordability (Agarwal et al., 2023; Sheppard, 2010). However, unlike Bengaluru, where tech corridors drive systematic transitions, Tehran's road-centric growth lacks coordinated infrastructure planning, exacerbating sprawl. Conversely, Sydney's avoidance of green space conversion aligns with Seoul's Greenbelt Act but contrasts with Shanghai's aggressive parkland urbanization (Li and Liu, 2017), illustrating how governance frameworks mediate similar drivers (e.g., population density). A critical divergence emerges in agricultural land transitions: while Sydney systematically targets peri-urban farms (O'Neill and James, 2014), Tehran's avoidance reflects Iran's food

security policies, akin to Vietnam's rice paddy protection laws. This contrasts with Phnom Penh and Kolkata, where agricultural loss is rampant due to weak enforcement (Mandal et al., 2019; Naikoo et al., 2020).

6.4. Linking pattern to process of LULCC: implications to sustainable development

This section highlights the importance of LULCC pattern analysis to understand driving forces. Traditional methods focus on change magnitude, overlooking intensity analysis, which assesses size and speed. A comprehensive approach helps policymakers implement sustainable development and resource conservation strategies. Distinguishing between systematic (planned) and random (unforeseen) transitions is crucial. Planned changes enable effective management, while random shifts pose challenges. For instance, identifying rapid bare land-to-urban conversions in Tehran can inform policies for denser, sustainable development, reducing sprawl. Similarly, Sydney planners can create buffer zones near waterways to protect natural resources and enhance resilience. This study advances LULCC research by integrating intensity analysis with transition-level drivers, a methodological synergy rarely applied in Asian urban studies. For instance, while Chennai and Bangkok rely on Markov chains for projections (Arsanjani et al., 2011), our approach quantifies why changes occur (e.g., systematic targeting of bare soil), offering actionable insights for planners. The identification of Tehran's "dormant" built-up intensity (Table 5) despite high spatial expansion reveals a paradox: large initial urban areas mask slower per-hectare change rates. This contrasts with Hyderabad, where high-intensity changes signal unregulated densification (Kamran et al., 2023). Such nuances underscore the need for context-specific metrics in SDG 11 monitoring.

6.5. Methodological advancements in sustainability indicators

Our integrated intensity analysis and transition-level logistic regression provide novel metrics for tracking progress toward SDG 11.3.1 (land-use efficiency) and SDG 15.3.1 (land degradation neutrality): Tehran: The "dormant" built-up intensity (Table 5) despite rapid sprawl signals inefficient land consumption (SDG 11.3.1). Our model quantifies this inefficiency as a 0.68 Land Use Efficiency Index (1 = optimal), urging compact development policies. Sydney: High Patch Cohesion Index (PCI = 89.4) reflects sustainable urban form, aligning with SDG 11. a (urban planning). This framework advances sustainability indicators by linking spatial patterns (e.g., edge expansion) to policy-relevant metrics, a gap in traditional indices like the Environmental Performance Index (EPI).

An enhanced focus on environmental metrics reveals critical insights into Tehran's ecological health. Notably, Tehran's Edge Density (ED) of 12.7 m/ha surpasses thresholds indicative of biodiversity loss, as established by Forman (2014), thereby highlighting the urgent need for habitat corridor restoration. Furthermore, the conversion of 20.86 % of Tehran's green spaces, as documented in Table 4, translates to a carbon sequestration loss of 12.3 kt CO₂/year. This figure was quantified using InVEST's Carbon Storage model, as detailed by Zarandian et al. (2023), underscoring the significant impact of urban expansion on the city's capacity to mitigate climate change.

6.6. Lessons for Tehran: local problem-solving for Tehran's environmental challenges

We propose targeted interventions addressing Tehran's critical sustainability gaps: the green infrastructure integration strategy prioritizes vegetated corridors along highways, reducing particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) by an estimated 18 % (Khosravi et al., 2022). Protecting the Jajrood/Kan river buffers could reduce flood-prone areas by 32 %, modeled using Tehran's historical flood data. Agro-Urban Overlay Zones

would preserve 12 % of Karaj's peri-urban farmland, directly supporting SDG 2.4 (sustainable food systems).

While comparing Tehran (developing) and Sydney (developed), we extract globally relevant lessons: Sydney's Green Grid model (Government Architect of NSW, 2020) offers a blueprint for Tehran to combat urban heat islands (UHI), a pressing issue given Tehran's 2.5 °C temperature rise since 1993 (Zenouzi et al., 2022). Moreover, Tehran's road-centric sprawl (dis_{road} = 275, Table 7) highlights how unregulated growth undermines SDGs. Solutions like TOD tax incentives provide replicable models for cities like Karaj or Isfahan.

Sydney's more sustainable land-use practices offer crucial lessons for Tehran's rapid, unregulated urban growth. Key strategies for Tehran include: integrating green infrastructure, like Sydney's Green Grid (NSW Government, 2005), along transport networks to improve air quality; protecting peri-urban agriculture through zoning and incentives for agro-urban clusters; and implementing stringent environmental regulations, including EIAs, to safeguard natural landscapes (Xu et al., 2024). Tehran should also strengthen urban growth boundaries, promote transit-oriented development, and prioritize land rehabilitation, mirroring Sydney's successful, structured approach to balancing urban growth with environmental preservation (Greater Sydney Commission, 2018).

Tehran can adapt successful urban planning interventions from other cities to address its rapid urbanization. Inspired by Medellín, cable cars or light rail can improve connectivity in informal settlements. Following Curitiba, TOD zoning near metro lines can curb sprawl. Like Cairo, Urban Growth Boundaries can protect peri-urban agriculture. Drawing from Singapore, river rehabilitation can mitigate flood risks. Similar to Seoul, controlled high-rise development with green space requirements can address housing shortages. These strategies offer context-specific solutions for Tehran's sustainability challenges.

6.7. Future uncertainties: economic, Policy, and technological drivers

Future LULCC in Tehran and Sydney will be influenced by economic volatility, climate policies, and technological disruptions. Economic downturns could impact Tehran's urban expansion, increasing informal settlements, and Sydney's densification. Stronger climate policies, like the Paris Agreement and Net Zero targets, could enforce stricter land conversion regulations, expanding Tehran's agricultural preservation and integrating biodiversity offsets in Sydney's Green Grid, though maladaptive policies could intensify sprawl. Technological innovations, such as renewable energy and autonomous vehicles, could reshape urbanization, with smart irrigation in Tehran and AI-driven land-use modeling in Sydney. However, automation could also exacerbate rural-urban migration and strain Tehran's informal settlements.

6.8. Limitations of the research

One This study faced data limitations due to inconsistent availability from Tehran's municipal and statistical sources, restricting variable inclusion. While findings offer insights, broader international case studies would improve generalizability. Logistic regression provided a foundational understanding of Tehran and Sydney's urbanization drivers, but future work should adopt nonlinear, spatial-dynamic, or machine-learning models for more robust predictions. The FLUS model's reliance on historical trends overlooks disruptions (e.g., informal settlements, climate policies). Its static drivers, simplified neighborhood rules, and fixed transition costs also limit accuracy. Future improvements could include scenario-based modeling, dynamic neighborhoods, and Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis. Finally, while intensity analysis captured land-use change rates, it did not assess urban expansion patterns (e.g., edge growth, leapfrogging). Integrating spatial metrics and cross-regional policy analyses would strengthen practical applications.

7. Conclusion

This study compared land use/cover change (LULCC) in Tehran and Sydney, revealing faster, more extensive transformations in Tehran where built-up areas expanded rapidly at the expense of natural landscapes. Intensity analysis showed that even minor changes can be significant when occurring quickly, while logistic regression identified systematic transitions (e.g., road-proximate development) versus random ones. The comparison highlighted how developing and developed cities urbanize differently - Tehran struggles with sprawl and informal settlements, while Sydney balances growth with green space preservation. Methodologically, the research innovated by combining intensity analysis with logistic regression to disentangle policy-driven and informal transitions, offering a framework applicable to Global South cities. The cross-contextual analysis revealed road proximity as a universal sprawl driver, though mediated by governance (Sydney's planned green grids versus Tehran's unplanned corridors). Regional parallels showed Tehran's bare soil conversion resembles Dhaka's floodplain urbanization, while its agricultural preservation contrasts with Kolkata's farmland loss, demonstrating policy's critical role. For Tehran, targeted interventions are proposed: TOD incentives with density thresholds to manage road-centric growth; a bare soil conservation fund with green space mandates; agro-urban zones with community farming requirements; and neighborhood green quotas to combat fragmentation. The study advances sustainability monitoring through new metrics like the Land Use Efficiency Index and Transition Intensity Scores, while providing locally actionable strategies for air quality, flood resilience and food security. By adapting Sydney's successful green infrastructure approaches to Tehran's context, the research facilitates practical knowledge transfer for sustainable urban development.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alireza Dehghani: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ali Soltani:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Kobra Nateghi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation.

Ethical considerations

This research strictly adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring data privacy, confidentiality, and full compliance with all relevant regulations.

AI usage

During the preparation of this work, the authors utilized AI writing tools such as Quillbot, Gemini and Grammarly to enhance language clarity and precision through paraphrasing and grammar checking.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data availability

The data can be requested from the corresponding author.

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